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of EXPRESSION

A Creative Folio

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Dr. Jessica Cano-Alorro, CHP

BSHM Program Chairperson/Assistant Professor IV
College of Management, Northwest Samar State University
Rueda St., Calbayog City, Samar, 6710., Philippines
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Our Gentle Giant

Our firstborn child, our heart's first light,
The one who filled our world so bright.
A happiness no words can say,
You came and took our breath away.

You were the joy we first embraced,
The love that time cannot erase.
The very first dream in our hands,
The beginning of all our plans.

The first grandson, so dearly known,
A precious gift the family has grown.
Your name, **Edan**, was born from love so true
From Editha's grace and Danilo's virtue.

And **Jestin**, the name we gave with pride,
From Jessica and Martin side by side.
Two hearts, one hope, one family's dream,
Woven together in your name's sweet theme.

Once a baby so small and dear,
Who filled our days with laughter and cheer.
But time has passed, as time will do,
And slowly our little boy grew.

Now you stand both tall and strong,
A gentle giant all along.
A loving son, so kind and true,
A pride and blessing through and through.

A caring brother your siblings admire,
A guiding light, their quiet fire.
Through every step and all you do,
Our endless love walks close with you.

For no matter how grown you may become,
Or how far your life may roam,
You'll always be our first great joy
Jestin Edan, our precious boy.